

INTEGRATING APPLICATION OF SINGAPORE STANDARDS IN A CHEMICAL ENGINEERING MODULE

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Abstract

This paper presents work done in integrating the application of Singapore Standards into the chemical engineering curriculum, specifically a core Year-3 module in the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) entitled *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention*. The paper firstly presents readers with a general overview that focuses on the importance of Standards in engineering education, and the issues and challenges faced in teaching them to students. These include lack of familiarity of lecturers with standards education, the nature of standards themselves which are often dry and boring to learners, the inter-disciplinary nature of standards, and different purpose served to different learners, and difference emphasis among those tasked with teaching standards. The paper next shares how the use of Singapore Standards is introduced into the chemical engineering module. Fundamentally, the approach is consistent with the CDIO (conceive, design, implement, operate) approach used by DCHE since its adoption in 2007. We defined the learning outcomes as awareness of relevant standards pertinent to chemical process safety, and able to identify relevant applicable sections of these standards, and make good recommendations to address chemical process safety issues based on the requirements spelt out in the standards. Four standards most relevant to chemical and process safety are chosen. A case study approach is adopted and an assignment (worth 15% of total module assessment) is designed that depicts a scenario that students are likely to encounter in a work environment. A set of rubrics based on the learning outcomes are developed. Working in teams of 4-5 members, students need to identify up to four to six separate issues related to chemical and/or process safety from the case. For each issue, the most applicable Singapore Standards that address the issue needs to be identified, and all four standards must be referenced at least once. The paper then presents the results of a student survey to determine their learning experience in using the Singapore Standards. Lastly, the paper concludes with discussion of the findings from the survey and measures we will take to further enhance the use of standards in chemical engineering education.

Keywords: *Chemical Engineering, CDIO, Integrated Curriculum, Singapore Standards*

Introduction

According to ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004, a “Standard” is a document “established by consensus and approved by a recognized body that provides for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results aimed at achieving the optimum degree of order in a given context.” Technical standards or engineering standards are formal documents that determine uniform engineering, technical, performance and interoperability criteria, methods, processes and practices. These standards are developed and promulgated by various agencies and technical associations such as the American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME), American Petroleum Institute (API), Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), etc. Among the uses of standards are the setting of specifications at the onset of a design, defining constraints during the detailed design process, and serving as benchmarks during testing. Standards can even take the effect of law if they appear, for example, in building codes.

Engineering Standards are an integral and arguably critical part of professional engineering practice, regardless of engineering discipline. Practicing engineers who value safety, mitigation of liability, and in most cases, customer acceptance, would not think of undertaking an engineering project without first considering applicable standards and legislation (Murphy, et al, 2007). Inclusion of engineering standards in engineering curriculum is now a requirement for program accreditation by the U.S. Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET). Criterion 4 of the Criteria for Accrediting Engineering Programs requires students to use engineering standards in the major design experience.

Kelly (2003) noted that there are extensive materials readily available to assist faculty in including engineering standards in the major design experience. ASME, for example, publishes examples on uses of codes and standards for students (Balkey, et al, n.a.). However, given the pervasive inclusion of standards in the practice of professional engineering, there is a lack

of teaching of standards in engineering education (Forbes & Emplincourt, 2003).

Standards Education: Issues and Challenges

Verman (1973) has called for the education for standards back in the 1970s. Introducing standards in the classroom will augment the learning experience by pointing students to available design tools, and to best industry practices. Student knowledge of standards would facilitate the transition from classroom to workplace by aligning educational concepts with real-world applications and market constraints. However, there are several significant challenges to standards education. One is the fact that in many cases the lecturers themselves are not familiar with standards and their role. Many may assume that standards education belongs only to the area of continuing education (Cooklev, 2013). Getting access to standards can also prove to be a tricky and expensive endeavour (Kozak, 2014). Other challenges include the following:

- J Standards are written in a formal language, which is very difficult to read and understand. This formal language is the reason why some consider standards boring.
- J The material to learn is very significant. Every year, in every technical area, hundreds, if not thousands, of pages of new standards are being published.
- J Standards change and evolve rapidly. In fact, standards evolve more rapidly than the underlying technical area.
- J Standards are inter-disciplinary in nature: they often require expertise in more than one technical area. In addition, knowledge of and use of standards also requires understanding of issues such as government regulations, ethics, intellectual property, etc

In a study by Khan et al (2013), in response to the question “What are the impediments to teaching and learning about technical standards?” one hundred forty-two respondents answered as follows:

- J Lack of text books that provide the fundamentals and examples of application of technical standards (62%)
- J Cost of access to technical standards documents (56%)
- J Lack of faculty expertise on application of standards (49%)
- J Lack of access to technical standards documents (42%)
- J The “other” (21%) responses include: limited time, too many standards to teach, lack of faculty time, standards are continuously changing, standards use complex language, and lack of standards knowledge by faculty and administrators.

Interestingly, as noted by De Vries and Egyedi (2007), incorporating standards in regular education courses has been much more actively accomplished in countries such as Korea and China and less in the Europe and the United States. Hesser and De Vries (2011) commented that “at the national level, South Korea is far ahead in implementing standardization

education in academic curricula. It does more than Europe as a whole.” Acyl and Borde (2003), in a survey on standardization education in Europe, reported very little effort was done in relation to training and education in this area. Krechmer (2007) reported on the 2004 survey on engineering schools by the U.S. Center for Global Standards Analysis, that standards education is not a priority issue, and that they do yet not accept the critical nature of standards in the new 21st century global economy. Choi and De Vries (2011a) shared South Korea’s University Education Promotion on Standardization (UEPS) as a case study for the country’s success in implementing standards education. Current academic courses on standardization have not been as successful as desired (Krechmer, 2007). This may be due to the lack of agreement on what constitute standards education. Krechmer (2007) opined that some standardization courses are fragmented by attempts to address in a single course three real, but separate, needs:

1. Teaching a non-technical audience the importance of standards, which is often unsuccessful because they usually do not see a need to learn about standards
2. Teaching technical students what they need to know about standards in their field is more likely to be successful
3. Teaching people who are planning to attend specific standardization committees in the near future on the policy and procedures of individual standardization committees

Olshefsky (2008) noted that presently standards are being used in university curricula, but typically the focus is on the standard’s technical requirements and not on the process of a standard’s development, and opined that students who learn about the process of developing standards are more likely to participate in their development and add value for future employers. In agreement, Krechmer (2007) also argued that academic courses would be better to focus on teaching the theoretical rules that underlie standards and use specific standardization examples for demonstration that the rules function as proposed. Lemes (2015) on the other hand, suggested that it is important to retain the generality of a course, to help students develop skills of understanding, and using standards in practice. The author also highlighted the lack of books on standardization available in the market; provided a brief review of some, and called for inclusion of standardization in engineering curricula, at least as an elective course. De Vries (2003) proposes the basic learning module in standardization, starting with examples of standards, first simple, then business-to-business examples, followed by generalization topics which include definitions, advantages, types of standards, decision-making, and the standardization process.

Integrating Singapore Standards into a Module

A Singapore Standard (SS) is a voluntary standard. It undergoes a full consensus process, including a two-month long public review before publication. A Singapore Standard becomes a mandatory standard

when it is referred to by the regulatory bodies in legislations, e.g. in the Singapore Civil Defence Force's Fire Code or in the Ministry of Manpower's Workplace Safety & Health Act (source: www.spring.gov.sg). A Singapore Standard is developed by SPRING Singapore, the national standards body, who work closely with the Singapore Standards Council and other Standards Organizations.

The module in this case study is entitled *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention*, a Year 3 Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) core module (60 hours, fully in-course, i.e. no examinations) taught to all 120 students in Semester 1 of an academic year. The module is taught using a flipped classroom format (Cheah, 2016) over a period of 15 weeks using case study as the core pedagogic method. Contact hours are 4 hours per week which is devoted to classroom activities designed to engage students in applying the concepts learned during the pre-class components. This work represents an independent learning assignment for students, and is worth 15% of their total grade.

The integration of Singapore Standards into *Plant Safety & Loss Prevention* follows a 'classic' CDIO approach used in DCHE (Cheah et al, 2013), which focuses on the following key questions (Crawley, et al, 2007):

- J What is the full set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that engineering students should possess as they leave the university, and at what level of proficiency?
- J How can we do better at ensuring that students learn these skills?

To address the first question, we first reference the learning aims of the module, and identify the suitable Singapore Standards. There are indeed many standards relevant to chemical process safety, and we narrowed it down to four, as shown in Table 1. SS 506 and SS 586 are already covered in *Plant Safety & Loss Prevention*, but only in very descriptive nature. The addition of 2 more standards make the learning process more comprehensive.

Table 1. Singapore Standards used in Case Study

Standard	Title
SS 532 (2007)	Code of Practice for The Storage of Flammable Liquids
SS 586 (2014)	Specifications for Hazard Communication for Hazardous Chemicals and Dangerous Goods
SS 506 (2013)	Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) Management System - Part 3
SS 603 (2014)	Code of Practice for Hazardous Waste Management

Next, we take into consideration students' prior knowledge of using standards of any kind (not limiting to the four above, and not limited to Singapore Standards), and reviewed the covered of standards in the 3-year DCHE curriculum. Perhaps not surprisingly, the two standards that students can most readily identify with are ISO 9001 and ISO 14001, as these are the

standards adopted institution-wide. They are less knowledgeable about other standards. It turned out that teaching of standards is at best "patchy", with no coherent approach to develop student understanding in their studies. In some topics where use of standards is clearly applicable, but these are only mentioned in passing, or not addressed at all.

We decided that the use of case study for standards education is most appropriate, as reported by Choi and De Vries (2011b) in their review of empirical data collected from 118 educational programs about standardization from 21 countries. These authors found that student learners at all levels preferred case studies, group activities, and hands-on experiences for their teaching modalities. We defined the learning outcomes for this work as awareness of relevant standards pertinent to chemical process safety, and able to identify relevant applicable sections of these standards, and make good recommendations to address chemical process safety issues based on the requirements spelt out in the standards.

As we are unable to find suitable existing case studies that meet our needs, we proceed to design our own. The resulting case is based on a scenario of an existing chemical company making bulk chemicals wanted to diversify into making specialty chemicals. Sufficient background information is given to students of both processes, and narratives for the standards were created and posted on YouTube. Working in teams of 4-5 members, students need to identify up to four to six separate issues related to chemical and/or process safety from the case. For each issue, the most applicable Singapore Standards that address the issue needs to be identified, and all four standards must be referenced at least once. This is to ensure that every student will contribute to the case, to minimize free-riders in the team. All four standards can be assessed online via special arrangement made by the author with SPRING Singapore. Students need to provide supporting evidence to support the issues cited based on information available from the case and choice of standard, and finally make recommendations of suitable actions to be taken, using the format shown in Figure 1.

		For Lecturer Use Only
Issue	(Your entry here)	
Standard	(Your entry here)	
Evidence	(Your entry here)	
Recommendation	(Your entry here)	
Total Marks		

Figure 1. Submission Requirement for Assignment

To ensure students are familiar with the expected learning outcomes, students are provided with the marking rubrics as shown in Table 2; and we took them through a marking exercise using the rubrics based on a sample answer we provide. They are obviously prohibited from using the sample answer in their submission, and were given up to 2 weeks to complete the assignment.

Table 2. Marking Rubrics

Category	Level 3	Level 2	Level 1
Issue Identify relevant issues	Issues are clearly identified and explained. (3 marks)	Issues identified but lack some clarity in explanation. (2 marks)	Issues are vague or unclear; no attempt at explanation. (1 mark)
Standard Identify relevant Standard	Reference made to correct Standard and cited the most relevant paragraph(s). (3 marks)	Correct Standard identified, but reference not made to most relevant paragraph(s). (2 marks)	Wrong Standard cited, or correct Standard cited but reference made to wrong or irrelevant paragraph(s). (1 mark)
Evidence Use of information from the scenario provided.	Very good use of evidence, clearly linked to issue identified, and make relevant reference to specific information provided in the scenario. (5-6 marks)	Partial or incomplete use of evidence, or made with only partial or incomplete reference to specific information provided in the scenario. (3-4 marks)	No evidence is used, or evidence used is weak or wrong; and are based on just stating the generic statements without making direct reference to specific information provided in the scenario. (1-2 marks)
Recommendation Make concrete and useful suggestions for follow-up actions the company should take	Specific suggestions given, addressing issues raised and meet requirements stipulated in the relevant Standard, which is explained using one's own words. This is further reinforced by specific reference to other relevant Standard(s). (6-8 marks)	Suggestions given, but incomplete in addressing the issue identified, or merely reproducing word by word what had been stated in the relevant Standard. Another relevant Standard cited but lack clarity on specific requirements on the cited Standard. (3-5 marks)	Suggestions are weak, not addressing issue identified, or completely missed the issue altogether, or not addressing requirements of the relevant Standard, or merely used general broad statements. Suggestions are limited to within the one standard as identified earlier. (1-2 marks)

We carried out a simple survey to determine their learning experience in using the Singapore Standards. We used a combination of 5-point Likert-scale and open-ended questions. A total of 92 students responded. The main findings are shown in Figures 2 to 6. Based on these findings, we can consider our effort as quite successful.

Figure 2. Usefulness of Assignment in Understanding Applicability of Standards

Figure 3. Realism in Scenario to Convey Importance of Standards

Figure 4. Usefulness of Narratives in Supporting Learning Standards

Figure 5. Usefulness of Sample Marking & Rubrics in Conveying Expectation

Figure 6. Student Preference on How to Integrate Standards into Curriculum

Of special interest to us is the result shown in Figure 6, as it has implications for the broader prospect on how standards education can be deployed in a wider scale. For this questions, students are to select which of the 3 options below will they prefer, if teaching of standards is to be included in their education:

A: Standalone (i.e. separate) fully in-course module, taught in class, with generic exercises

B: Pre-recorded narrative (like SS 586), available in Blackboard, for use in any module(s)

C: Integrated into suitable module(s) in similar manner as that for *Plant Safety & Loss Prevention*

As can be seen from Figure 7, there is no one way to introduce standards into an engineering curriculum, with a sizeable number of students (32.61%) still prefers a formal classroom-type teaching. The good sign is that more than half (51.09%) are comfortable with reading about standards on their own, and confident about applying them in other modules. We believe this is a workable approach to widens the use of standards in engineering education.

Discussion

Choi and De Vries (2011b) noted that the learning objective of standardization education programs at primary and secondary levels were mainly to raise awareness of the importance of standardization in real-life settings, while that of higher education was to

develop specialized knowledge and theory of standardization. At the diploma level, we need to focus on giving students more exposure to the use of relevant standards in their study, and opportunities to practice their applications in selected case studies, or assignments as was done for a core module as described in this work. However, given the already packed curriculum, it will not be desirable to add another standalone module on standards (Option A in the previous section). We would like to suggest a “staged” approach using combinations of Options B and C, as follows: For the first and second years of study we design assignments such as the approach presented in this work, to strengthen their awareness and understanding of applicability of relevant standards within the various modules studied. As in this work, students are guided to specific standard(s) needed for their assignments. Partnership with our library is also another approach to increase awareness of and access to standards (Gbur & Solomon, 2016). For example, the library can support campus-wide seminars featuring invited speakers from industry or standard bodies (e.g. SPRING Singapore), as well as development of online tools for frequently-used standards as we had done for SS 586. Then, at the third year of study, we challenge them to apply appropriate standards to their capstone (final year) project (e.g. Kelly et al, 2005) and/or internship project. In this case, students need to identify which standards are relevant on their own depending on the nature of project undertaken, and undertake the learning of these standards on their own. Students in capstone or internship projects can work directly with industry sponsors and benefit from their professional experience in standard identification as well as addressing client constraints (Leachman and Pezeshki, 2015).

Conclusion

This paper shares our experience in integrating Singapore Standards into a core chemical engineering module. Students’ learning experience had been positive. Moving forward, we will continue our partnership with SPRING Singapore to bring more standard education into the classroom. At the same time, we will work with the DCHE Course Management Team and industry partners to implement the abovementioned ideas for improvement. As noted by Harding & McPherson (2010), a collaborative effort between educational institution and businesses is essential to make required resources available and affordable for students.

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